

Palacký University
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The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region

EUVIP

Overview of Blogposts Published within the EUVIP Project

1. 1. 2023 – 31. 12. 2025

Funded by
the European Union

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Overview of the project

Project title	The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region
Project acronym	EUVIP
Project number	101079069
DOI	10.3030/101079069
Funding	HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme
Program	HORIZON.4.1 - Widening participation and spreading excellence HORIZON.4.1.2 - Twinning
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Website	www.euvip-project.com
Coordinator	Palacký University Olomouc (UP), ROR: 04qxnmv42 University of Helsinki (UH), ROR: 040af2s02
Partners	UCLouvain (UCL), ROR: 02495e989 University of Copenhagen, ROR: 035b05819 (until 2023-08-31) Lund University, ROR: 012a77v79 (from 2023-11-01)
Start date	2023-01-01
End date	2025-12-31
Project summary	<p>Through its concise training, research, communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities EUVIP will significantly contribute to shaping the new, rapidly developing academic field of Indo-Pacific Studies. The project will raise the awareness of the stakeholders (academia, civil society, politics, and broad public) of the strategic, political, and economic significance of the volatile Indo-Pacific region for Europe and for a values-based European approach towards this region. Together with its seven dissemination partners, the EUVIP consortium will create a sustainable European Indo-Pacific experts network and knowledge hub with strong dissemination channels to national and EU policymakers in order to strongly contribute to the EU's Indo-Pacific strategy and policies. In addition, EUVIP will establish a Myanmar Centre at Palacky University in Olomouc (Czech Republic) to connect academia with politics and the civil society. EUVIP will build on UP's strong expertise on Southeast Asia and China's Belt and Road Initiative, supplemented by the</p>

complementary expertise of three leading European research partners (University of Helsinki, University of Copenhagen, and Université Catholique de Louvain). To further improve UP's excellence capacity and resources, the three expert partners will provide training to UP's early career researchers, PhD students, and research management administrators. This transfer of knowledge will result in a much higher international visibility of UP academics through an increased number of publications in world-class journals, an increased number of Horizon 2020 project applications, an increased reputation and attractiveness of UP for renowned international scholars and students, and increased mobility and employability of the UP staff.

Overview of blogposts

Blogpost goal

Disseminate, communicate and exploit the innovative research results in EUVIP member states and at EU level

Related to

Project objective 4, Work package 4 (Task 4.2)

List of blogposts published by project member

1. **Rejtova, Eunika; Kironska, Kristina;** *Taiwanese Not Satisfied With Their Government's Handling of the Pandemic, Survey Reveals*; CEIAS; 2023-02-16; <https://ceias.eu/taiwanese-not-satisfied-with-their-governments-handling-of-the-pandemic-survey-reveals/>
2. **Kironska, Kristina;** *Taiwan and Africa: a comprehensive overview of diplomatic recognition and derecognition of the ROC*; CEIAS; 2023-09-07; <https://ceias.eu/taiwan-and-africa-a-comprehensive-overview/>
3. **Gerstl, Alfred;** *The EU's de-risking strategy and its Global Gateway Initiative: Two strategic responses to China's Belt and Road Initiative and the China-CEEC cooperation*; CEIAS; 2023-09-12; <https://ceias.eu/the-eus-de-risking-strategy-and-its-global-gateway-initiative/>
4. **Lickova, Veronika; Kironska, Kristina; Chen, Kuan;** *Taiwan's quasi-diplomatic interactions with Europe: representative offices*; CEIAS; 2023-12-14; <https://ceias.eu/taiwans-quasi-diplomatic-interactions-with-europe/>
5. **Kironska, Kristina;** *Taiwan Elections 2024 Explained: What to Expect?*; CEIAS; 2024-01-14; <https://ceias.eu/taiwan-elections-2024-explained-what-to-expect/>
6. **Cidale, Federica;** *Zainichi Koreans in Japan: Exploring the Ethnic Minority's Challenges*; CEIAS; 2024-02-26; <https://ceias.eu/zainichi-koreans-in-japan-exploring-the-ethnic-minoritys-challenges/>
7. **Cidale, Federica;** *Is Japan giving up on pacifism?*; CEIAS; 2024-08-01; <https://ceias.eu/is-japan-giving-up-on-pacifism/>
8. **Broul, David; Nenutil, Antonín;** *Has South Korea found its firm foothold in Central Europe?*; CEIAS; 2025-02-11; <https://ceias.eu/has-south-korea-found-its-firm-foothold-in-central-europe/>
9. **Cidale, Federica;** *Recognizing ethnic agency in Myanmar: From CIA operations to the Spring Revolution*; CEIAS; 2025-10-13; <https://ceias.eu/recognizing-ethnic-agency-in-myanmar-from-cia-operations-to-the-spring-revolution/>
10. **Cidale, Federica;** *Japan's shifting perceptions of cybersecurity*; CEIAS; 2025-11-06; <https://ceias.eu/japans-shifting-perceptions-of-cybersecurity/>